

A review on tribal land rights in Bangladesh.

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Abstract: In this article, I have tried to write about the land and land rights of the tribal communities of Bangladesh. An attempt has been made here to present a picture of what kind of rights are given to them under the laws of Bangladesh and what the actual situation there is. I have taken the help of various research articles, statutes, and newspapers to write this article.

Introduction:

Aborigines have been inhabiting or existing in a land since the earliest times, or from before the arrival of colonists or indigenous communities. They have been living and living their lifestyle since before the arrival of other tribes in that land. They have a right to the land that other people do not have. There are many such communities in Bangladesh. Example: Chakma, Marma, Garo, Khasia, Santal etc. The government has enacted various laws to ensure their right to land. I will outline those rights and the extent to which they are being implemented.

Indigenous and Tribal People:

“Indigenous and tribal peoples” is a common denominator for more than 370 million people, found in more than 70 countries worldwide. Indigenous and tribal peoples have their own cultures, languages, customs and institutions, which distinguish them from other parts of the societies in which they find themselves.

Indigenous and tribal peoples are often known by national terms such as native peoples, aboriginal peoples, first nations, adivasi, janajati, hunter-gatherers, or hill tribes. Given the diversity of peoples it aims at protecting, the Convention uses the inclusive terminology of “indigenous and tribal peoples” and ascribes the same set of rights to both groups.¹

In Bangladesh, they are treated as 'tribals' in official documents, though in the Act 12 of 1995 and Rules 6, 34, 45, 50 of Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) Regulation (1900), they are documented as 'indigenous peoples' or 'aboriginal' as per section 97 of the SAT Act (1950).²

The Constitution of Bangladesh ensures affirmative action for indigenous peoples and prohibits discrimination inter alia on grounds of race, religion or place of birth, Article 23A of which provides, “the

¹ 'Indigenous and Tribal Peoples' <www.ilo.org>.

² State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950.

State shall take steps to protect and develop the unique local culture and tradition of the tribes, minor races, ethnic sects and communities”.³

Traditional Land Distribution Method of Tribal people:

While the land ownership of plains tribals is determined by the customary laws of the country, tribal land ownership in the three hill districts is social. The principle of 'universal property ownership rights' is the basis of their land ownership. As a result, this ownership is oral from generation to generation. It is managed by the headmen and karbaris of hill districts under three circles. But in the last 30 years, the amount of land under the control of this hill town has decreased by 51 percent.⁴

Land Rights of Tribal People in Colonial Era:

Chittagong Hill Tracts Regulations, 1900 (Act-1 of 1900 AD) popularly known as Chittagong Hill Tracts Manual. It is a law enacted by the then British Government of India that mainly deals with the policies on how to manage the Chittagong Hill Tracts, located in the southeastern region of present-day Bangladesh. The previous Act passed in 1860 was not sufficient - this Act was passed in place of that Act due to the government's realization.

The main features of Chittagong Hill Tracts Manual were:

- No non-hill persons (persons not residing in hilly areas) can enter the Chittagong Hill Tracts unless he holds a permit issued at the discretion of the District Commissioner (DC). The District Administrator reserves the right to expel any person who is not an adivasi (tribal) of the district who is found to be obstructing/harmful to the peaceful administration of the district.
- In future no one will be allowed to hold more than 25 acres (10 hectares) of land (under one lease or under multiple leases). And land can only be given on lease to hill men. However, if a non-hill farmer is a permanent resident of a hill village, he can be leased to that village.
- Registration Act-1908 shall not apply to Chittagong Hill Tracts. Rules 12-33 of the Regulations deal with matters relating to the principles of the Registration Act.
- Three Circle Heads of the three Circles will be appointed for the administration of their respective Circles. Every person living or cultivating in a circle would be subject to the jurisdiction of the circle head or king rather than being responsible to the government officials, his family, traders and market shopkeepers. Headmen are responsible for the administration of the Mauza (the smallest revenue collection unit in a district) and are appointed by the DC on the advice of Sub-Divisional Officers, Circle Heads or Rajas and residents of the Mauza. No land case can be settled or transferred without the recommendation of the Headman.⁵
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³ The Constitution Of Bangladesh.

⁴ 'Land Rights of Tribal Community'.

⁵ The Chittagong Hill Tracts Regulations, 1900 .

Land Rights of Tribal People in Contemporary Situation:

The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act of 1950 provides special rules for transfer of land to tribals. Any transfer of land without complying with that rule will not be a valid transfer in the eyes of law and will not create any right in favor of the transferee. Who is meant by Adivasis and the special procedures to be followed in transferring their property are detailed in the Act.

If the tribal raiyat wishes to transfer to a person belonging to a tribe or class other than the tribe, the tribal raiyat must apply to the revenue officer for permission to transfer his property. On receipt of such application, the Revenue Officer, having regard to the provisions of section 97 of the Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 and the existing provisions of the Land Reforms Ordinance, 1984, shall, if he thinks fit, allow the applicant tribal or tribal raiyat to transfer his property.

Transfer should be done through registry deed

Sub-section 4 of Article 97 states that if the tribals want to transfer their land, it should be done through a registry deed. If for any reason a tribal has to transfer his land before land registration then in that case written consent should be obtained from the Revenue Commissioner as per the deed and as per the date of transfer.

Special rules for land closure of tribals

Sub-section 5 of Section 97 states that a tribal can transfer his land only as a 'complete usufructury mortgage'.

In a complete foreclosure bond, possession of the property is given to the mortgagor, the mortgagor receives the rent and profits of the mortgaged property in lieu of the mortgage money and interest, the mortgagor does not assume any personal liability for the payment of the money, and the mortgagor cannot foreclose or sue for sale of the property.

Sub-section 6 of section 97 states that the term of the usufructuary mortgage shall be for a maximum period of 7 (seven) years and shall be registered. But if a tribal wants to take loan from Agricultural Development Corporation or any Co-operative Society for availing agricultural loan then the applicable percentage shall not apply. In other words, other types of mortgage mentioned in the Transfer of Property Act can be kept in addition to the complete usufructuary mortgage in case of borrowing from such financial institution or cooperative society.

In addition, through the hill peace agreement of 1996, the interests of the tribal community have been protected. There are restrictions on the acquisition of property by Bengalis and there is talk of improving their standard of living. It has been said that the government will take appropriate measures to ensure that their land is not dispossessed and a land dispute resolution board will be formed.⁶

⁶ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 .

Hill Land Dispute Settlement Commission and it's Restrictions:

Common people are disappointed with the inability of Chittagong Hill Tracts Land Dispute Settlement Commission. Nobody can do anything. Because of this, the common people's frustration towards the Land Commission has increased.

There are dual land settlements in the hills; The government has made this commission to solve those problems. The government has given this power to the commission through the law. But this commission could not give the expected results due to various reasons. It has been sent to the government for framing of rules. It remains to be seen whether the work progresses further.

After the signing of the Hill Agreement, the government enacted the 'Chittagong Hill Tracts Land Dispute Settlement Commission Act' in 2001 to settle land disputes. The Act was amended in 2016. But after the amendment of the law, the rules of the commission were not framed. In this situation, the land dispute settlement work is stopped. After amending the Act, the Commission started functioning and invited applications from the owners of the disputed land. But the commission could not start work due to non-formulation of rules. Then comes the coronavirus infection. The work of settling land disputes in three hill districts has come to a standstill.⁷

Land Rights of Tribal People Under International Law:

In 1957, a convention was held by the International Labor Organization for the purpose of preserving the rights of these human groups of the world in terms of ethnic self-identification, social, cultural and economic. In this convention the Aboriginal and Tribal Peoples Convention -1957 (107) was adopted. The section adopted in 1989 was amended to 1989 (169). In this way, steps were taken to give equal rights to the indigenous people by adopting two clauses to protect the rights of the indigenous peoples by the United Nations Labor Organization. Its main objective was to recognize the cultural identity, rights to land, rights to territory or natural resources and citizenship of minority and indigenous peoples worldwide.⁸

Comparative Analyses:

Despite having so many laws in Bangladesh, they are losing land. Their land is being dispossessed. The administration is playing the role of a silent spectator.

The reasons and solutions for these issues will be shown here-

- Political population transfer and forced migration process is a poor communal political tool These include Kaptai Dam, National Park Declaration, Eco-Park and various oppressive works The latest Madhupur forest was cleared and leased forest land to non-tribals Thus numerous tribal villages and settlements have disappeared.

⁷ 'On the Settlement of Land Disputes in the CHT' <www.thedailystar.net>.

⁸ The Aboriginal and Tribal Peoples Convention ,1957.

- Construction of national parks, eco-parks, social forestry projects on tribal lands and areas without any opinion or consent of tribals.
- Declaring or expropriating lands traditionally owned and used by tribals as reserve forests without informing the tribals.
- Harassment and extermination of tribals with eviction notices and hundreds of false cases.
- Enemy Property or Vested Property Act.
- Forged documents of land grabbers, forced land acquisition.
- Government land office corruption and adversarial treatment of indigenous peoples.
- Corruption and forced payment of bribes during land survey; Expropriation of land if bribe is not paid.
- Not getting legal recourse, even if the case is won, not getting possession of the land.
- Losing more land, destitute and penniless in years and even ages of litigation.

How tribal land can be saved -

- Amending the constitution to recognize the rights of indigenous people and ensure their right to self-determination, including their right to land and resources;
- Establishment of independent land commissions for the tribals of the plains.
- Implementation of Chittagong Hill Tracts Land Commission.
- Taking steps for the development of indigenous peoples and ensuring their meaningful participation and ensuring international standards in this regard
- Implementation of the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples and ILO Convention No. 107 and Rectify 169.
- Enact the Indigenous People's Rights Act.

Conclusion:

According to the report, the government has taken several steps to protect native aboriginal's rights, but many of them have not yet been put into effect. Without abiding by these regulations, various groups are annexing tribal lands and robbing them of their rights. Both Bangladeshi law and international law are broken by them. Government should investigate these problems and solve those problems. Government should educate the populace about these problems.

References:

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